

MEDIA LITERACY AND THE EVOLUTION OF INFORMATION CULTURE AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN SOCIETY.

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ANNOTATION

Forming the culture of using the media space, the Internet and social networks among young people is the foundation of today's modern information space and is an integral part of human social and cultural life. Because the concept of information is specific to space and time, it appears in various forms as a periodic phenomenon. Nowadays, due to the increased flow of information in society, the process of "getting tired of" information, consuming it without analyzing it, has arisen. The urgency of understanding, evaluating and forming critical thinking of information received in the global information space is explained.

Key words: media, literacy, information, culture, evolution, society, technology.

Media literacy is a set of skills that enable people to analyze, evaluate, and create different media forms and messages. A person with high media literacy will be able to easily notice which source is reliable and which source is spreading false news. Media literacy is a set of skills that enable people to analyze, evaluate, and create different media forms and messages. A person with high media literacy will be able to easily notice which source is reliable and which source is spreading false news. In other words, media literacy is the ability to apply critical thinking skills to the messages and symbols conveyed through the media. The media is a powerful force in the lives of young people. Music, television, video games, magazines, and other media have a powerful influence on how we see the world, often beginning in childhood. In order for consumers to critically analyze media, they must develop media literacy skills and habits from childhood will need to be developed. These skills include accessing media at a basic level, analyzing it critically based on specific concepts, evaluating it based on that analysis, and finally producing the media itself. This process of learning media literacy skills is called media education. The promotion of media education in the 21st century was recognized by UNESCO as a priority direction of cultural and educational development, and it was emphasized that

media literacy can be increased in this way. UNESCO supports media and media literacy to improve people's critical thinking and decision-making. The organization seeks to build the capacity of politicians, educators, media professionals, youth organizations and vulnerable populations in this field, and assists member states in formulating national media and information literacy policies and strategies.

Understanding of information. The word "information" is pending or pending indicates information about past events. In everyday life, every specialist works with different information. The concept of information is interpreted differently in several disciplines. For example: in philosophy, information is used as a category that affects the human mind, reflects and drives objective reality. In the science of cybernetics and informatics, information is used as a criterion for increasing knowledge about an event or reducing uncertainty. In the activity of using computers, information is used as an object that performs management functions. The concept of information is inextricably linked with the concept of information, but not all information is information. In order for all information to become information, it should represent all the features of the event.

Currently, all information can be relatively divided into the following types: technical information; agrobiological information; political information; legal information; economic information and others. All information has the following characteristics: Continuous generation. Representation of letters in numbers. Discrete character. Together with the appearance of living beings on the earth, it is very important to know and receive information about their development, environment, events, determine living conditions based on this information, and understand the progress of development. In addition, over time, during the study of nature by people, information about the machines, devices, measuring devices, and technological processes being created and used was added to this information. Twenty or thirty years ago, it was very easy to define what information is. Information is considered to be information transmitted between people, and in the future, it has become of great importance for planning and managing production, as well as for determining living conditions and the level of economic development. Information is considered to be information transmitted between people, and later it became of great importance for planning and managing production, as well as for determining living conditions and the level of economic development.

For example, while the car is moving, the sound of the engine is different. For passengers in the car, this is not important, but for a qualified driver, this information

is considered, and based on this, he determines the condition of the engine based on the sound coming from the engine.

So, in order to briefly answer the question of information, it is necessary to refer to the connection between two objects, the source and the consumer.

The information technology industry complex consists of computers, communication systems, data warehouses, knowledge warehouses and related fields of activity. Examples of rationalizing information technologies are ticket booking and hotel accounting systems. Creative (creative) information technologies consist of systems that produce information, use it and include a person as a component.

Modern development and achievements of information culture inform all spheres of science and human activity without showing the necessity. Informatization of the society is understood as the use of information as a wealth of the society, which ensures the development of the economy, the scientific and technical development of the country, and the acceleration of the processes of democratization and intellectualization of the society.

In fact, informatization of society is considered an objective process related to increasing the role of intellectual activity in all aspects of human life. Informing the society serves to improve the standard of living of the people of our republic, to meet social needs, to increase the economy and to accelerate the development of science and technology. Information culture is a unique phenomenon in the life of a person and society. According to him, information is a means of gathering knowledge about the world around us, providing the opportunity to adapt to the conditions of existence of a person and society, and they based on this, people and society choose the right course of action in order to satisfy their needs and realize their interests. Information communication forms the basis of training, education and formation of a person. Information conveys the content of social and technical norms to a person, it about the possible negative consequences of not following these norms is the only means of warning. Today's people are everyday cannot imagine his life without information or news. Modern media The audience receives a huge amount of information in space every day. In fact, current topics and events happening in the world, we follow the events first through the mass media. In this regard, promptness to the audience, principles such as objectivity and accuracy are of primary importance.

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